

IN SITU MONITORING OF THERMALLY CYCLED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES USING LASER EXTENSOMETRY AND NEUTRON DIFFRACTION.

Mark R. Daymond and Philip J. Withers
Department of Materials Science and Metallurgy, University of Cambridge
Pembroke Street, Cambridge, CB2 3QZ, UK

ABSTRACT

The thermal cycling behaviour of SiC short fibre reinforced Al matrix composites has been investigated by both scanning laser extensometry and neutron diffraction. Three dimensional unit cell finite element models have been produced, allowing for matrix deformation both by creep and plasticity. Comparison of the experimental results with model predictions has allowed conclusions about the dominant deformation processes operating at different parts of the thermal cycle to be drawn.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The addition of a stiff reinforcement phase, typically a ceramic, to a metal alloy matrix has proved to be an effective way of producing materials of high specific stiffness. The two phases of the metal matrix composite (MMC) will typically have widely differing coefficients of thermal expansion. As a result, when a MMC undergoes a change in temperature, the different thermal expansions cause misfit strains and thus induce internal stresses. Even for small thermal excursions these internal stresses can exceed the room temperature yield stress and cause localised yielding around the reinforcements. These stresses become especially important under thermal cycling fatigue when they are regenerated each cycle, and can drive superplastic deformation of the composite to large strains (>300%), under even small applied loads. There is thus considerable interest in the investigation of the thermal cycling behaviour of MMCs both with respect to their use in thermally cycled environments and for the exploitation of thermal cycle superplasticity for the forming of MMC components.

The aim of the work described in this paper has been to gain an understanding of the stresses and deformation processes occurring in the two phases of the composite during thermal cycling. We have used scanning lasers to monitor the external dimensions of a specimen both perpendicular and parallel to the loading axis. This allows the determination of a differential Poisson's ratio which can give an insight into the dominant method of deformation. Secondly neutron diffraction has been used to monitor lattice spacing in the two phases of the MMC, again both parallel and perpendicular to the loading axis. This allows the determination of stresses within each phase of the composite. Previously, because of the slow rates of data acquisition, neutron studies have been confined to unrealistically slow cycle rates. Our results have been obtained using a novel stroboscopic measurement system.

2.0 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The MMC examined in this work was a 10vol% silicon carbide approximately 1 μ m diameter whisker reinforced commercially pure aluminium matrix composite, produced by a powder route and extrusion method. SEM examination of the microstructure of the composite showed that the processing had produced a high degree of alignment of reinforcement, but also breakage of the whiskers resulting in a volume averaged whisker aspect ratio of around five. Two thermal cycles

were employed, both with a 150°C temperature range, ramp rates of 30°C/minute and 100s dwells, giving a 800s cycle period. The cycle ranges used were 175-325°C and 200-350°C. The imposed load (25 MPa) was applied by the use of a dead weight.

2.1 SCANNING LASER EXTENSOMETRY

Experimental investigation of thermal cycling in MMCs has been restricted in most cases in the past to monitoring of the macroscopic extension of samples, sometimes combined with subsequent sectioning and microstructural investigation [1]. In order to monitor the effects of thermal cycling on both the axial (i.e. parallel to loading axis) and transverse dimensions of an MMC an infra-red heating rig has been developed, based on an earlier design by Furness & Clyne [2]. The use of radiant heaters, combined with a continuous flow of nitrogen gas onto the sample, allows accurate and rapid variation of the specimen temperature. The specimen is machined with flanges as shown in Fig. 1, and a scanning laser monitors the changes in distance between the flanges throughout each cycle. A second laser, scanning in the perpendicular direction measures the specimen cross sectional width, allowing a calculation of a differential Poisson's ratio ($-\text{d}\epsilon_{\text{trans}} / \text{d}\epsilon_{\text{axial}}$).

Figure 1. The specimen geometry showing the specimen design and the position of the scanning lasers. The temperature is monitored by a thermocouple placed in a hole in one of the flanges.

2.2 NEUTRON DIFFRACTION

The use of x-ray diffraction to determine lattice spacing and hence internal stresses using Bragg diffraction is well established (e.g. [3]). Neutrons of appropriate wavelength will also undergo elastic scattering, with the added advantage of a bulk penetration of the sample (e.g. ~70mm in Al for neutrons, compared to ~140µm for x-rays of comparable wavelength). This allows the monitoring of the mean strain in the bulk material. Our experiments have been carried out at a pulsed 'time of flight' source. At such a source a fixed detector angle and a range of wavelengths (i.e. neutron velocities) is used [4]. The neutrons' time of flights can then be related to lattice spacings by the known instrument geometry. Each pulse produces an entire diffraction profile which is added to subsequent pulses until the total intensity is large enough to be analysed using a Rietveld peak fitting method [5] to give the lattice spacing. The strain is given in terms of the time shift of the diffraction peaks: $\epsilon = \Delta t / t$. Placing the specimen loading axis at 45° to the neutron beam with detectors at 90° to the beam on both sides of the specimen, allows the monitoring of lattice plane spacing both parallel and perpendicular to the specimen axis [4].

The pulsed method is particularly suited to composite materials because both phases of the composite can be monitored simultaneously (provided of course that the unit cell dimensions are not too similar). Comparison to initial, or ideally stress free, values of lattice spacings then allows the calculation of strains and thus, once stress free thermal expansion effects have been removed, the stress can be determined. It is clear that by its very nature this technique will monitor only $\epsilon_{\text{nonplastic}}$ where $\epsilon_{\text{nonplastic}} = \alpha\Delta T + \epsilon_{\text{elastic}}$. The stress free lattice spacing and the coefficient of thermal expansion (α) of the aluminium matrix were determined by neutron diffraction measurements of an unloaded, unreinforced matrix specimen at various temperatures between 25°C and 350°C. The stress free lattice spacing of the SiC at room temperature was also determined, but due to time shortages, the CTE could not be determined and a published value was used [6].

One of the major problems with neutron sources at present is the low intensity of neutrons presently available, requiring experimental times typically of the order of 10mins - 1 hr to produce statistically significant results. In contrast thermal cycling studies have mostly been carried out with short period cycles, of the order of 5 - 15 minutes. The data acquisition problem is further exacerbated by the desire to resolve the strain changes which occur during the cycle. Previous work has been restricted to long period (1 day) thermal cycles [7, 8]. To overcome the relatively

low count rates, we have developed a novel stroboscopic data collection system as part of the ENGIN strain scanner [9]. The thermal cycle is divided into a number of segments, typically 8 or 16. Neutrons collected during each segment are stored separately giving 8 or 16 separate diffraction profiles representing the mean lattice spacings during that time segment. Neutrons from the n^{th} segment of the next cycle are added to the diffraction profile of the n^{th} segment of the first cycle and so on for the following cycles, until enough neutrons have been collected to produce statistically significant results. This stroboscopic data collection system relies on the fact that the material behaviour varies very little over many cycles. That this is true has been observed at both a macroscopic [1] and microstructural [10] level. We have also carried out experiments to confirm that the mean stresses observed in the two composite phases during a cycle do not vary appreciably over a large number of cycles.

3.0 THE FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Finite element (FE) models have been used for some considerable time for the modelling of large scale structures but in recent years have been adapted to the modelling of micro-scale structures (e.g. [11]). One of the major problems involved with producing such a model is representing the random nature of the arrangement of reinforcements found in real composites, as well as the distribution of reinforcement size. Clearly modelling a real distribution of reinforcements would place huge demands on computing time. The approach followed is therefore to approximate the random array by a regular array of identical reinforcements. The appropriateness of this approach has been discussed elsewhere [12].

The phases of the composite are modelled as having the same properties as the monolithic constituents. Some authors have noted a change in the ageing behaviour and microstructures of the matrix brought about by the introduction of the reinforcement phase [13], but this only seems to be important for precipitation hardening alloys, whereas the matrix used here is commercially pure Al. It should be noted however that since the material was produced by a powder metallurgy route, oxide stringers are present along the matrix grain boundaries, with Al_2O_3 making up 0.8% by volume of the material [14]. This affects the matrix properties, improving the high temperature yield stress and increasing the creep rate sensitivity to stress. Material data for the matrix was therefore taken from tests carried out by Clauer and Hansen [14] on an unreinforced matrix produced by the same route.

Figure 2. Transverse and longitudinal sections illustrating the aligned reinforcement distribution considered in the FE modelling.

Two three dimensional fibre arrangements were modelled, a staggered and aligned case as proposed by Levy [15], of which the latter is shown in Fig 2. The details of the models are given in more detail elsewhere [16]. Two basic matrix material constitutive laws have been applied. Firstly the matrix has been modelled as a perfectly plastic material (model \odot), including the temperature dependence of yield stress [14]. As has been observed by Pickard and Derby [10], after a few cycles of settling down, the matrix dislocation structure in a composite at any given point within a cycle, is virtually unchanged over many cycles. This suggests that we should model the matrix as a kinematically hardening material, which then 'recovers' during the hot part of the thermal cycle (i.e. microstructurally, dislocations build up during the deformation and then annihilate when the temperature is raised) and such a constitutive model is currently under development. The use of a hardening plasticity model without this recovery however, produces a gradual build up of hardening, which results in a decrease in the deformation per cycle, as compared to the steady state deformation observed experimentally. This problem has been avoided in this paper by the use of a perfect plasticity model. A slightly elevated yield stress (158MPa at 25°C), comparable to the stress observed in the hardening model after a few cycles has been used to avoid 'softening' the composite behaviour too much. Secondly, a power law creep model with

stress exponent $n = 6$ and an activation energy of 390 kJ mol^{-1} [14] has also been used, in conjunction with perfect plasticity (model ②). In order to mimic the real composite stress state more closely, residual thermal stresses equivalent to a production temperature of 350°C were initially applied to the unloaded composite.

4.0 RESULTS

It should be noted that the experiments detailed here represent cycles of relatively small thermal excursion and the ratchetting observed per cycle is therefore small. These cycles were deliberately chosen to allow a large number of cycles i.e. several hundred, to be carried out on the specimens without any problems with the development of material damage or specimen failure.

4.1 NEUTRON DIFFRACTION

The results below (Fig. 3) show the development of axial elastic strain in the two composite phases during the $175\text{-}325^\circ\text{C}$ cycle. The stress free thermal (i.e. $\alpha\Delta T$) changes in lattice spacings have been removed.

Figure 3. Variation in axial elastic strains in both phases during the $175\text{-}325^\circ\text{C}$ cycle

Figure 4. Al axial elastic strain in $200\text{-}350^\circ\text{C}$ cycle measurements showing the hysteresis loop and also its development with consecutive cycles.

The errors tend to be larger in the SiC phase principally due to the smaller scattering volume of SiC present within the specimen. The extrusion process during manufacture of the composite produces a high degree of alignment of the whiskers and also considerable texture in the Al. This greatly increases the diffracted intensity in the axial direction, resulting in much smaller errors for the lattice spacings than are found in the transverse direction. The axial stresses determined by consideration of the triaxial stress state therefore tend to have correspondingly larger errors than the axial strains. The elastic strains shown in Fig. 3 however represent a variation in axial stress in the Al of $\sim 70 \text{ MPa}$, and in the SiC of $\sim 590 \text{ MPa}$.

In interpreting the shape of Fig. 3 we need to consider a number of effects. When considering the stresses it should be borne in mind that we are trying to interpret a three dimensional system using strain measurements in one direction. For instance this means that a zero axial elastic strain does not necessarily correspond to zero axial stress. Nonetheless conclusions can be drawn regarding the stress state of the composite. The two phases are strained axially by the imposed load, which if we ignore thermal and plastic effects would produce an axial strain of $275 \mu\text{strain}$ in the Al and $160 \mu\text{strain}$ in the SiC (elastic FE model). This explains why the two curves do not cross at zero strain. Secondly, differential thermal expansion leads to elastic misfit strains and hence to a linear decrease in the tensile strain in the Al phase and the compressive strain in the SiC as the temperature is raised and the reverse when it is lowered. The inelastic relaxation of axial strain is most obvious during the high temperature dwell. If we define the stress free temperature (T_{sf}) to be the temperature at which the thermal stresses are zero, we would expect from consideration of the relative magnitudes of the transverse strains that T_{sf} should be close to the cross over of the Al

and SiC curves. This would result in values of ~ 260 and $\sim 275^\circ\text{C}$ in the heating and cooling ramps respectively. This hysteresis in T_{sf} was also noted by Withers [7, 8] where, due to the much larger ΔT employed in the cycle, the hysteresis was larger. In that material T_{sf} after fabrication appeared to be around 100°C . T_{sf} gives an indication of the relaxation state of the material and the increase in T_{sf} can be attributed to the continuous nature of the cycling.

The clear hysteresis effects in the two ramps can be observed however in the $200\text{-}350^\circ\text{C}$ cycle, as shown in Fig. 4. Here the strain is plotted as a function of temperature. In this experiment only 8 points have been produced per cycle and there is a thus a loss of time resolution. The four loops shown represent four consecutive summation periods taken during a fifty hour experiment. An examination of the strains suggests that if there is a decrease in the observed elastic strain at the top end of the cycle with time, it is of a magnitude comparable to the limit of the resolution available here. From a stress balance argument we would expect an opposite trend to occur in the SiC phase, but the larger errors present in the SiC observations makes such a comparison impossible. This result does however seem to justify our earlier assumption used in applying the stroboscopic data collection system, in that the changes in strain observed over the cycle summation period are small enough to be ignored.

4.2 LASER EXTENSOMETRY

Examination of the results produced by the laser extensometry is complicated by the difficulty of removing the thermal expansion effects i.e. determining the composite elastic coefficient of thermal expansion. Our FE model results have shown that even a small increase in temperature can cause localised yielding around reinforcement corners and therefore the experimentally determined composite CTE would be expected to be affected by some inelastic effects. This effect was minimised by the use of a small thermal excursion carried out at a lower temperature. Nevertheless this resulted in a measured axial CTE of $19.8 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, which should be compared with the an elastic FEM value of $18.8 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, and Eshelby [8, 17] determined value of $18.2 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$. In the determination of the inelastic strains, the FEM value of composite CTE was employed.

The inelastic effect is clearly larger in the higher temperature cycle as would be expected (Fig. 5). In the cooler cycle the deformation starts to increase at nearly halfway up the heating ramp ($\sim 240^\circ\text{C}$), increasing rapidly before levelling out just below the hot dwell ($\sim 290^\circ\text{C}$). The decrease in plastic strain during the cooling ramp appears to be more gradual. In the hotter cycle, the deformation starts and plateaus earlier in the cycle, before again appearing to reverse and slope more gradually during the cooling ramp.

The gradient of the steep rise seen about 1/3 of the way through the heating ramp in the $200\text{-}350^\circ\text{C}$ cycle is equivalent to a CTE of $\sim 4 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, so it is unlikely to be completely due to error in the composite CTE. We are therefore seeing inelastic deformation relatively early in the heating ramp, which does not continue into the top of the heating ramp and hot dwell. We would expect that, due to thermal strains, as the temperature increases, the reinforcement becomes tensile in the axial direction relative to the matrix. This may result in a constraining and limiting of the axial extension. In the cooling ramp the yield is more gradual and occurs to a lower temperature. This behaviour may also be explained by consideration of the stress states induced by the temperature change. The reinforcement will be placed into compression by the temperature change and this will tend to constrain contraction of the specimen. This increased deformation at the low temperature end of the cooling dwell is also predicted by the FE model (Fig. 7) and discussed in §4.3.

As has been noted above and in previous work [2], the evaluation of an elastic composite CTE, and hence the determination of the inelastic response, is extremely difficult and is undoubtedly complicated by the relatively large variation of aluminium CTE with temperature. The approach taken here therefore, is to try and obtain information directly from the measured dimensions. To this end we have determined the differential Poisson's ratio from the macroscopic composite strains. We have averaged the results from many consecutive cycles in order to try to reduce the noise. Fig 6 shows the Poisson's ratio response for the heating and cooling ramps of the $200\text{-}350^\circ\text{C}$ cycle. The horizontal line indicates the elastic value predicted by Eshelby [8, 17] (i.e. $-\text{CTE}_{\text{trans}}/\text{CTE}_{\text{axial}}$). It should be noted that though the axial and transverse CTE values change with temperature, their ratio is fairly independent of temperature change. Though the plot is clearly noisy, a number of features reoccur in the examination of similar plots determined at other points within the cycling history of the specimen. Firstly, there is a clear drop in the Poisson's ratio at the

high temperature region of both cycles, though this drop is larger during the heating ramp. During the heating ramp the fall in Poisson's ratio starts at around 280°C, but during the cooling ramp it continues until around 260°C, again indicating some hysteresis in the cycle. Then as the cooling ramp continues the Poisson's ratio continues to rise. Thus the deformation is essentially elastic in the middle of the cooling ramp and for all but the high temperature part of the heating ramp.

Figure 5. Axial non-thermal strains for both cycles as determined by the lasers. The dwells are indicated by the shaded regions.

Figure 6. Poisson ratio variation during the 200-350°C cycle showing differences between heating and cooling ramps. The behaviour during the dwells is shown schematically in the insets.

Consideration of the changes in Poisson's ratio occurring during tensile loading gives some appreciation of how the Poisson's ratio changes monitored here may be occurring. We would expect an increase in the ratio during tensile loading (the FE model suggests that an elastic ratio of $\nu = 0.27$, tending to $\nu = 0.45$ for fully plastic matrix deformation). This suggests that the increase in Poisson's ratio noted towards the end of the cooling ramp is probably due to bulk plasticity, and indeed the FE models indicate that large areas are plastically deforming during this part of the cycle. In the aligned model this is found in the areas between the fibre lengths. It is even more obvious in the staggered model, where a continuous band of plastic deformation extends between the fibre ends and between unit cells. The decrease in Poisson's ratio found at the higher temperatures means that there are much larger transverse expansions than expected in an elastic system, which is indicative of a relaxation of hydrostatic stress, possibly caused by more localised yielding along the fibre length and particularly around the fibre ends as is indicated in the FE models. What we may be seeing therefore is two regimes, the former (bottom of cooling ramp) where the deformation is principally a bulk plasticity deformation and the latter where though there is some bulk contribution, the dominant mode is a more localised creep deformation.

4.3 FE MODEL RESULTS

Fig 7. summarises the development of axial inelastic composite strain over the cycle as predicted by the FE model, showing the mean inelastic strain in the matrix. The figure shows clearly how the introduction of creep into the model alters the form of the plastic deformation. In the plasticity only model $\textcircled{1}$ this is approximately symmetric resulting in very little net plastic strain per cycle. The addition of creep, which is dominant at the top of the heating ramp and during the hot dwell, drives the plastic deformation towards the bottom of the cooling ramp, resulting in a larger increase in net plastic strain. This is of particular interest when compared with the Poisson's ratio measurement (Fig. 6) which suggest that inelastic deformation is occurring over the same part of the cycle.

The modelled Poisson's ratio results (Fig. 8) mimic some of the features obtained experimentally. Firstly, there is an indication of deformation at the top of the heating ramp and also at the base of the cooling ramp, as would be expected from Fig. 7. The magnitude is however smaller and the sense of the change at the end of the cooling ramp is reversed. The model also shows a much smaller decrease in Poisson's ratio during the high temperature part of the cooling ramp than is experimentally observed. The most likely cause for this would seem to be the use of a lower creep

rate in the model than was experimentally determined. The high stress exponent ($n=18$) observed by Clauer [14] in the unreinforced matrix poses considerable difficulties to finite element modelling because it can result in huge differences in creep strain rate across an element for a relatively small stress variation. An approach is being developed to overcome this, but the results shown were produced with a reduced exponent. This may well have reduced the creep effect observed during the initial part of the cooling ramp. Modelling work carried out using material parameters appropriate to Al that was not oxide dispersion strengthened [16], did show a drop in Poisson's ratio in the high temperature end of the cooling ramp that was of a magnitude comparable to that seen in the heating ramp.

Figure 7. Inelastic strain development during the 200-350°C cycle showing driving of plasticity towards end of cooling ramp for models (1) and (2).

Figure 8. Poisson's ratio variation during 200-350°C cycle predicted by FEM for the creep and plasticity model (2). The behaviour during the dwells is shown schematically in the insets.

The modelled elastic strains show quite a high level of agreement with experiment, as shown in Figs. 9. Noticeably however, the absolute values are slightly displaced. The reinforcement is too compressive and the matrix too tensile. One possibility of course is that the stress free lattice parameters have been incorrectly determined, but this seems unlikely, at least for the SiC. We should therefore consider the possibility that we have introduced too much initial residual thermal stress into the system during the modelling, i.e. the apparent temperature drop in the model is larger than that determined experimentally (with the model $T_{sf} \sim 320^\circ\text{C}$). A reduction in the initially applied thermal stress would bring the curves together. Due to constraints in available computer time, the FE model has only undergone a few cycles and this may also have affected the results.

Figure 9. Comparison of FE model predictions (lines) with neutron results (points and error bars) for the 175-325°C cycle.

Figure 10. Comparison of FEM results with neutron results for 200-350°C cycle.

The model predicts the relative change in elastic strains during the cycle very well. There is a slightly steeper gradient in the experimental results than the model, and we again see evidence that the creep rate may be being underestimated in the model; the degree of relaxation during the hot dwell appears to be considerably larger in the experimental results. Secondary features of the

models such the gradual flattening of the gradients of elastic strain towards the end of the cooling ramp are too small in magnitude to be picked out with the present experimental errors.

For clarity the modelled strains in Fig. 10 have been shifted such that the SiC and Al results cross at the same strain as the experimental results. We see that the degree of hysteresis predicted by the model is slightly smaller than that seen experimentally but that, as in Fig. 9 the gradients are basically correct.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper describes preliminary measurements carried out with a novel stroboscopic data collection system which has allowed the monitoring of short period thermal cycling deformation of MMCs. This, combined with Poisson's ratio monitoring, has given some insights into deformation mechanisms occurring through the cycles. FE modelling, while unable to produce the full composite response, can give an insight into the relative contributions of plastic and creep type deformations and how they may combine to produce thermal cycling ratchetting.

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